

5. Distortion of flag leaves and incomplete emergence of panicles are symptoms of ragged stunt disease.

6. Excessive panicles of infected plants at later growth stages are another symptom of ragged stunt.

be observed in the early regenerated growth; other symptoms appear at booting stage.

So far, studies of ragged stunt transmission through seeds and soil and by mechanical means have yielded no positive results, but the disease can be transmitted by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. The causal agent-vector interaction will probably be categorized in the persistent group. Although biotypes 1, 2, and 3 of the brown planthopper differ in their ability to attack rice varieties, no significant difference has been found in their ability to transmit ragged stunt.

The nature of the causal agent of the ragged stunt disease remains obscure. However, it is not a fungus, bacterium, nematode, or mite. It is probably a virus.

Under natural infection, the following varieties and lines of *O. sativa* were susceptible to ragged stunt: BG34-8, BG90-2, BG374-2, BKN6986-108-2, Gow Ruang 88, IR8, IR20, IR22, IR24, IR26, IR29, IR30, IR3839-1, IR4427-115-3-3-3-3, IR4547-16-3-7, IR4568-586-2-2, IR4625-169-3-3-3, IR4723-345-1-3-1, IR4744-32-1-3-3, KN-IB-461-8-6-9-2, Pelita I/1, and TN1. *O. latifolia* can also be infected.

Since the infection has been noted in rice seedbeds, protecting seedlings and plants during early growth would probably reduce the disease incidence.

Study indicates viral nature of rice ragged stunt disease

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Dip preparations and ultrathin sections of plants naturally infected with ragged stunt disease at the IRRI farm and artificially inoculated by viruliferous *Nilaparvata lugens* were studied with an electron microscope at Hokkaido University. Electron micrographs showed

Electron micrographs show virus particles in dip preparation (top) and in a phloem cell of an ultrathin section (bottom) of a rice plant infected with ragged stunt disease.

polyhedral particles of 50–70 nm. The particles appeared abundantly in phloem cells (see photo), and in cells of the vein-swollings, or galls.

Although the determination of the infectivity of the particles is still under way, the electron micrographs serve as additional evidence that the causal agent of rice ragged stunt disease is a virus.

Resistance to bacterial leaf streak in India

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Bacterial leaf streak, caused by *Xanthomonas translucens*, is sometimes widespread and damaging, causing losses comparable with those from bacterial blight; however, little has been done on the development of resistant varieties. Varieties have been screened by artificial inoculation under natural conditions at Pantnagar since 1973. These results are from kharif 1973 and 1975, when disease pressure was heavy.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in a puddled field with four checks: IR22 (resistant), Krisna (moderately resistant), IR8 (susceptible), and Cauvery (highly susceptible). The entries were inoculated at 45 days after sowing by rubbing bacterial suspension in cotton wool on the undersurface of the leaves. A spray inoculation increased disease pressure. Observations were recorded at the maximum-tillering stage and at 14 days after flowering on a scale of 1–9 (see table).

The following entries were recorded as resistant or moderately resistant to bacterial leaf streak:

KHARIF 1973

Resistant – SMI-6, RP 633, RP 189-2, OR 10-58, and OR 10-237.

Moderately resistant – IR579-119-2-3, CR 10R-157, ARC 5983, entries no. 6328, 6333, 6334, 6335, and 6336, RP 291-20, and RP4-13.

KHARIF 1975

Resistant – AD 1140, Hoyaku/Kolumba 540-1, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-5, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-6, Jikoku/Kolumba 540-7, Shiranui/Goinchiew 35-4, FH 487, MR 249, RP 1017-334-3-6,